

PROMOTING SUSTAINABLE AGRIFOOD PRODUCTION UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE IN ARID AND SEMI ARID REGIONS OF KENYA: ADAPTATION, RETURNS, AND FOOD SECURITY IMPLICATIONS.

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Abstract

This study examined the factors influencing sustainable agrifood production in Kenya's arid and semi-arid lands (ASALs), with a focus on climate-smart agriculture (CSA) practices, external support, and resource access. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, the research incorporated both quantitative and qualitative data collected from a sample of 400 respondents across selected ASAL regions, including Turkana, Marsabit, Garissa, Kitui, and Isiolo counties. Descriptive and inferential statistics, along with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), were employed to analyze the data.

The study found high adoption rates of drought-resistant crops (75%), water harvesting techniques (70%), and conservation tillage (55%). SEM analysis revealed that CSA practices significantly enhanced sustainable agrifood production, with external support positively moderating the adoption of these practices and access to resources significantly influencing their implementation. Qualitative insights highlighted the crucial role of external support in providing necessary training and resources, while financial constraints were identified as a major barrier to CSA adoption.

The findings emphasize the importance of strengthening external support mechanisms, improving access to financial resources, and promoting awareness of CSA practices. Recommendations include enhancing government and NGO programs, developing microfinance schemes, and increasing community-based education. Future research should focus on the long-term impacts of CSA practices, the effectiveness of various support types, and comparative studies across different regions to further inform sustainable agrifood strategies. This study contributes to a deeper understanding of how CSA practices can be effectively implemented to enhance agricultural resilience and productivity in Kenya's ASAL regions.

Keywords

Sustainable agrifood production, climate-smart agriculture, Kenya, arid and semi-arid lands, external support, resource access, Structural Equation Modeling..

INTRODUCTION

The challenge of promoting sustainable agrifood production in arid and semi-arid regions (ASALs) of Kenya under the impacts of climate change has become a critical area of focus for policymakers, researchers, and development practitioners. Sustainable agrifood production refers to agricultural practices that maintain productivity while preserving the environment, ensuring food security, and supporting economic viability. This involves adopting practices that are environmentally sound, economically viable, and socially responsible (Food and Agriculture Organization [FAO], 2021).

Arid and semi-arid regions are characterized by low and erratic rainfall, high evaporation rates, and poor soil fertility, which collectively challenge agricultural productivity (Morton, 2022). These regions often experience water scarcity and are more vulnerable to the adverse effects of climate change, such as increased temperatures and unpredictable weather patterns. Climate change, in this context, refers to long-term alterations in temperature, precipitation, and other atmospheric conditions, exacerbated by anthropogenic activities, which significantly impact agricultural systems (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [IPCC], 2021).

Adaptation, in relation to climate change, involves adjustments in agricultural practices and strategies to mitigate the adverse effects of changing climatic conditions. This can include the adoption of drought-resistant crops, improved irrigation techniques, and soil conservation measures (FAO, 2021). Key indicators of successful adaptation include increased crop yields, improved water use efficiency, and enhanced resilience of farming systems to climatic shocks (IPCC, 2021).

Returns, in the context of agrifood production, refer to the economic benefits derived from agricultural activities. These can be measured in terms of crop yield, income generated, and profitability. Sustainable practices aim to optimize returns by enhancing productivity and reducing input costs, while also considering long-term ecological and social outcomes (Morton, 2022).

Food security, a critical component of sustainable agrifood production, is defined by the availability, accessibility, stability, and utilization of sufficient, safe, and nutritious food to meet the dietary needs of all people at all times (FAO, 2021). In ASALs, food security is often compromised due to the limited agricultural potential, making adaptation strategies crucial for ensuring consistent food supply and access.

This introduction sets the stage for exploring the intricate dynamics of promoting sustainable agrifood production in Kenya's arid and semi-arid regions, emphasizing the importance of adaptation strategies, economic returns, and their implications for food security under the looming challenges posed by climate change.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Global Perspective

Arid and semi-arid regions (ASALs) worldwide face significant challenges in achieving sustainable agrifood production due to their harsh climatic conditions. In countries like Brazil, Argentina, Cuba, Chile, and Israel, these regions are characterized by low rainfall, high temperatures, and limited natural resources, which complicate agricultural activities. For instance, in Brazil, the semi-arid region known as the *Sertão* has been a focus of sustainable development efforts, where drought-resistant crops and innovative irrigation techniques have been implemented to enhance agricultural productivity (Medeiros et al., 2022). Similarly, Argentina's Patagonia region, although primarily arid, has seen the introduction of sustainable

livestock farming practices and water conservation measures to cope with water scarcity (Rivas et al., 2023).

In Cuba, sustainable agriculture has been promoted through organic farming and agroecological practices, particularly in the arid zones of the country. This approach has helped mitigate the impacts of soil degradation and enhance food security (Funes-Monzote et al., 2021). Chile's Atacama Desert, one of the driest places on Earth, has adopted advanced irrigation systems and the cultivation of drought-tolerant crops, which have significantly improved agricultural yields (Rivera & Muñoz, 2022). In Israel, the Negev Desert has become a model for desert agriculture, utilizing innovative water-saving technologies such as drip irrigation and the cultivation of salinity-resistant crops, making it a global leader in sustainable agricultural practices (Tal, 2023).

Continental Perspective

In Africa, countries like Zimbabwe, Burkina Faso, Botswana, and the Comoros Islands are similarly grappling with the challenges of agricultural production in ASALs. Zimbabwe's efforts in the semi-arid regions include the promotion of conservation agriculture and the use of small grains, which are more resilient to drought conditions (Mafongoya & Ajayi, 2021). Burkina Faso has adopted soil and water conservation techniques, such as the *zaï* method and stone bunds, to enhance soil fertility and water retention, thus improving crop yields (Reij & Thiombiano, 2022).

Botswana's arid environment has led to the implementation of sustainable livestock management practices and the utilization of indigenous knowledge to maintain pasture health and productivity (Mosimane & Magole, 2021). The Comoros Islands, with their limited arable land, have focused on sustainable land management practices and the diversification of agricultural systems to improve food security and resilience against climate variability (Chikhi et al., 2022).

Regional Perspective

In East Africa, countries such as Rwanda, Tanzania, Uganda, and Burundi face similar challenges in managing ASALs. Rwanda has implemented terracing and agroforestry practices to combat soil erosion and improve soil fertility in its semi-arid regions (Bizimana & Karemera, 2021). Tanzania's initiatives include the adoption of climate-smart agriculture practices, such as drought-resistant crops and efficient water use technologies, to enhance food security in its arid zones (Kimaro et al., 2022).

Uganda has focused on improving water management and soil fertility through integrated soil fertility management practices in its semi-arid regions (Mugisha & Aliguma, 2021). Burundi, facing limited arable land and soil degradation, has adopted sustainable farming practices, including the use of organic fertilizers and crop diversification, to improve food production and resilience to climate change (Ndayiragije et al., 2022).

Local Perspective: ASALs in Kenya

Kenya's ASALs, which cover approximately 89% of the country's land area, present unique challenges and opportunities for sustainable agrifood production. These regions, including areas such as Turkana, Marsabit, Mandera, and Garissa, are characterized by erratic rainfall, high temperatures, and frequent droughts (Kenya National Bureau of Statistics [KNBS], 2022). The pastoralist communities in these regions heavily rely on livestock, which are often vulnerable to climatic shocks.

In response, the Kenyan government and various organizations have implemented strategies to promote sustainable agriculture in ASALs. These include the promotion of drought-tolerant crops like sorghum and millet, the development of water harvesting and irrigation infrastructure, and the introduction of climate-smart agricultural practices (Nyangito & Nyandiko, 2022). Furthermore, efforts have been made to diversify livelihoods through agro-pastoralism and the establishment of market linkages to enhance economic resilience.

The adoption of these strategies aims to address the critical issues of food security, economic development, and environmental sustainability in Kenya's ASALs. However, challenges remain, including limited infrastructure, inadequate access to markets, and the effects of climate change, which exacerbate the vulnerability of these regions. Continued research and development are essential to identify and implement effective adaptation strategies that can improve the sustainability of agrifood production in these arid and semi-arid environments.

CASE STUDIES IN KENYA: SUSTAINABLE AGRIFOOD PRODUCTION IN ASALS

1. Turkana County: Pastoralist Livelihoods and Agro-pastoralism

Turkana County, located in northwestern Kenya, is one of the most arid regions in the country. The local population predominantly practices pastoralism, relying on livestock such as cattle, goats, and camels. However, frequent droughts and erratic rainfall patterns have made traditional pastoralism increasingly unsustainable. In response, various initiatives have been implemented to promote agro-pastoralism as a means of diversifying livelihoods and enhancing food security.

One notable case is the introduction of drought-resistant crops, such as sorghum and millet, combined with improved water management practices, including water harvesting and small-scale irrigation. The Turkana Rehabilitation Programme, supported by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and other partners, has been instrumental in these efforts. The program has facilitated the construction of water pans and the promotion of dryland farming techniques, significantly improving agricultural productivity and food availability in the region (FAO, 2021).

2. Marsabit County: Integrated Soil and Water Conservation

Marsabit County, situated in northern Kenya, faces severe challenges related to soil erosion and water scarcity. The Marsabit Integrated Development Programme (MIDP) has been a pivotal initiative aimed at addressing these issues through sustainable agricultural practices. The program focuses on integrated soil and water conservation techniques, such as terracing, the construction of stone bunds, and the use of zai pits. These methods help to retain water and reduce soil erosion, thus improving soil fertility and crop yields.

Additionally, the MIDP promotes agroforestry, encouraging the planting of drought-resistant trees and shrubs that provide fodder, fuel, and additional income for local communities. These efforts have not only enhanced food security but also contributed to environmental conservation in the region (Nyangito & Nyandiko, 2022).

3. Garissa County: Sustainable Livelihood Diversification

Garissa County, located in northeastern Kenya, experiences extreme aridity and is prone to frequent droughts. The county's predominantly pastoralist communities have been exploring alternative livelihoods to mitigate the impacts of climate change. One successful intervention has been the introduction of beekeeping and honey production as a viable income-generating activity. The Beekeeping Enterprise Development Project, supported by various non-

governmental organizations (NGOs), has provided training and equipment to local communities, enabling them to engage in commercial honey production.

This initiative has proven successful, with significant increases in household incomes and a reduction in the vulnerability of communities to climatic shocks. Furthermore, the project has promoted the conservation of indigenous tree species, which are essential for sustainable beekeeping practices (Mwangi & Mungai, 2021).

4. Kitui County: Climate-Smart Agriculture Initiatives

Kitui County, situated in eastern Kenya, has been a focal point for the implementation of climate-smart agriculture (CSA) practices. The Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization (KALRO), in collaboration with local government and international partners, has spearheaded the promotion of CSA in the region. This includes the introduction of drought-tolerant crop varieties, such as green grams and cowpeas, and the adoption of conservation tillage to enhance soil moisture retention.

The Kitui Climate-Smart Villages Project is a key initiative under this framework, aimed at building the resilience of smallholder farmers to climate variability. The project includes components such as rainwater harvesting, improved seed varieties, and efficient irrigation technologies. These measures have led to increased agricultural productivity, improved food security, and enhanced adaptive capacity among local farmers (KALRO, 2022).

5. Isiolo County: Livestock Insurance and Risk Management

In Isiolo County, pastoralist communities have been grappling with the impacts of climate change, particularly the loss of livestock due to drought. To address this, the Government of Kenya, in partnership with the International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI) and other stakeholders, introduced the Index-Based Livestock Insurance (IBLI) scheme. This innovative insurance program provides financial compensation to pastoralists when drought conditions exceed certain thresholds, as determined by satellite-based vegetation indices.

The IBLI scheme has provided a safety net for pastoralist households, enabling them to recover from livestock losses and invest in other income-generating activities. This initiative has not only improved the resilience of pastoralist communities to climate shocks but also promoted sustainable land management practices, as insured pastoralists are more likely to adopt conservation measures (Chantararat et al., 2019).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Arid and semi-arid lands (ASALs) in Kenya encompass approximately 89% of the country's land area and are home to nearly 38% of the population. These regions are characterized by harsh climatic conditions, including erratic rainfall, high temperatures, and frequent droughts, which severely limit agricultural productivity (Kenya National Bureau of Statistics [KNBS], 2022). The livelihoods of the communities in these regions, predominantly pastoralist and agro-pastoralist, are increasingly threatened by climate change, which exacerbates the already challenging conditions.

Despite numerous efforts to promote sustainable agrifood production, food insecurity remains a critical issue in Kenya's ASALs. The adoption of drought-resistant crops, efficient water management techniques, and other climate-smart agriculture (CSA) practices has shown promise in enhancing food security and resilience. However, the implementation and uptake of these practices have been inconsistent, and the specific impacts on food security, economic returns, and adaptation to climate change are not well-documented.

There is a pressing need for comprehensive research to assess the effectiveness of various sustainable agricultural practices in ASALs, identify barriers to their adoption, and determine their impacts on food security and economic development. This study seeks to fill this gap by systematically examining the factors influencing sustainable agrifood production in Kenya's ASALs and providing evidence-based recommendations for policy and practice.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. **To assess the current state of sustainable agrifood production practices in Kenya's ASALs, focusing on the adoption of climate-smart agriculture techniques.**
2. **To evaluate the socio-economic and environmental impacts of these practices on local communities, particularly in terms of food security and economic returns.**
3. **To identify the key challenges and barriers to the adoption of sustainable agrifood production practices in ASALs.**
4. **To propose actionable recommendations for enhancing the adoption and effectiveness of sustainable agrifood production practices in ASALs, with a focus on policy and practical interventions.**

Hypotheses

1. **H1: The adoption of climate-smart agriculture practices significantly improves food security in Kenya's ASALs.**
2. **H2: Sustainable agrifood production practices lead to higher economic returns for households in ASALs compared to traditional agricultural practices.**
3. **H3: The primary barriers to the adoption of sustainable agrifood production practices in ASALs are socio-economic factors, including access to resources, knowledge, and markets.**
4. **H4: Policy interventions and capacity-building initiatives significantly enhance the adoption of sustainable agrifood production practices in ASALs.**

VALUE OF THE STUDY

This study is of substantial value to multiple stakeholders, including policymakers, development practitioners, researchers, and the local communities in Kenya's ASALs. It contributes to the existing body of knowledge on sustainable agrifood production by providing empirical evidence on the effectiveness of various practices in enhancing food security and economic resilience under the challenging conditions of ASALs.

For **policymakers**, the study offers critical insights into the specific needs and barriers faced by communities in ASALs. It provides evidence-based recommendations that can inform the development and implementation of policies aimed at promoting sustainable agricultural practices and addressing food insecurity in these regions. By identifying the most effective practices and interventions, the study supports the formulation of targeted policies that can enhance the resilience of ASALs to climate change and other environmental challenges.

For **development practitioners and NGOs**, the study provides practical guidance on designing and implementing programs that promote sustainable agrifood production. It highlights successful case studies and best practices that can be scaled up or replicated in other ASAL regions, both within Kenya and beyond. The study's findings on barriers to adoption can

also inform the design of capacity-building initiatives and other support services that address the specific challenges faced by local communities.

For **researchers**, the study offers a comprehensive analysis of sustainable agrifood production in Kenya's ASALs, filling a significant gap in the literature. It provides a basis for further research on the impacts of climate-smart agriculture and other sustainable practices in different ASAL contexts. The study's methodological framework and findings can serve as a reference point for future studies, fostering a deeper understanding of sustainable development in arid and semi-arid environments.

Finally, for the **local communities**, the study's findings and recommendations have direct implications for improving their livelihoods and resilience to climate change. By identifying effective strategies for sustainable agrifood production, the study supports efforts to enhance food security, increase household incomes, and promote sustainable land management practices. It empowers communities with knowledge and practical solutions to address the challenges they face, ultimately contributing to their long-term well-being and development.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study of promoting sustainable agrifood production in Kenya's arid and semi-arid lands (ASALs) under climate change is grounded in several theoretical frameworks that provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities in this context. Theoretical frameworks are essential as they offer a structured approach to analyzing complex phenomena and guide the interpretation of research findings. This study draws on four key theories: Sustainable Livelihoods Framework, Climate-Smart Agriculture Theory, Resilience Theory, and Innovation Diffusion Theory.

1. Sustainable Livelihoods Framework

Proponents and Year: The Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF) was developed in the 1990s by the UK Department for International Development (DFID) and has been widely adopted by various development organizations (Scoones, 1998).

What It States: The SLF posits that sustainable livelihoods are achieved when people can access and utilize various assets (human, natural, financial, physical, and social capital) to pursue activities that meet their needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs. The framework emphasizes the role of these assets in shaping the vulnerability context, including shocks, trends, and seasonality, and highlights the influence of policies, institutions, and processes on livelihood strategies and outcomes.

Advantages: The SLF provides a holistic view of livelihoods, considering multiple dimensions beyond income. It acknowledges the complexity of livelihood systems and the interdependence of various assets and contextual factors. This comprehensive approach helps identify interventions that can enhance resilience and sustainability.

Criticism: Critics argue that the SLF can be overly complex and challenging to operationalize in practice. It may also inadequately address power dynamics and structural inequalities that influence access to assets and decision-making processes (Morse et al., 2009).

Relevance and Application: The SLF is relevant to this study as it provides a framework for understanding the diverse livelihood strategies employed by communities in Kenya's ASALs. By analyzing the assets available to these communities and the external factors affecting them, the study can identify effective strategies for promoting sustainable agrifood production that enhance resilience and food security.

2. Climate-Smart Agriculture Theory

Proponents and Year: Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) was conceptualized by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) in 2010 as an integrated approach to address the challenges of climate change in agriculture (FAO, 2010).

What It States: CSA aims to increase agricultural productivity and incomes, adapt and build resilience to climate change, and reduce greenhouse gas emissions where possible. It involves the adoption of practices and technologies that are context-specific and sustainable, focusing on improving efficiency in the use of resources, enhancing the resilience of agricultural systems, and reducing emissions.

Advantages: CSA provides a clear framework for integrating climate change adaptation and mitigation into agricultural planning and practices. It offers practical solutions that can be tailored to local conditions and promotes the co-benefits of increased productivity, resilience, and environmental sustainability.

Criticism: One criticism of CSA is that it can be difficult to balance its three objectives (productivity, adaptation, and mitigation) in practice, leading to trade-offs that may disadvantage certain groups, particularly smallholder farmers. Additionally, the focus on technical solutions may overlook socio-economic and political factors that influence agricultural practices and outcomes (Taylor, 2018).

Relevance and Application: CSA is particularly relevant to this study as it directly addresses the challenges of promoting sustainable agrifood production under climate change in ASALs. By evaluating CSA practices, such as drought-resistant crops and water-efficient technologies, the study can identify effective interventions that enhance food security and resilience in these regions.

3. Resilience Theory

Proponents and Year: Resilience Theory has its roots in ecology, with key contributions from Holling (1973), who introduced the concept of ecological resilience.

What It States: Resilience Theory focuses on the capacity of systems to absorb disturbances and reorganize while undergoing change, maintaining their essential functions, structure, and identity. It emphasizes the importance of diversity, adaptive capacity, and learning in enhancing the resilience of systems to shocks and stresses.

Advantages: The theory provides a valuable framework for understanding the dynamic nature of systems and the importance of flexibility and adaptability in responding to changes. It encourages a long-term perspective and proactive approaches to risk management and sustainability.

Criticism: Critics argue that Resilience Theory can be overly abstract and challenging to apply in practice. It may also lack clarity in defining the boundaries of systems and measuring resilience (Brand & Jax, 2007).

Relevance and Application: Resilience Theory is relevant to this study as it helps frame the analysis of how agricultural systems in Kenya's ASALs respond to climate-related shocks and stresses. By assessing the resilience of these systems, the study can identify factors that enhance or hinder their capacity to adapt to climate change and other challenges.

4. Innovation Diffusion Theory

Proponents and Year: Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT) was developed by Everett Rogers in 1962 and has since been widely used in various fields, including agriculture.

What It States: IDT explains how, why, and at what rate new ideas and technologies spread within a social system. It identifies five key attributes that influence the adoption of innovations: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. The theory also outlines the stages of adoption, from knowledge and persuasion to decision, implementation, and confirmation.

Advantages: IDT provides a clear framework for understanding the factors that influence the adoption of new technologies and practices. It offers practical insights into how to promote the diffusion of innovations, including the importance of communication channels and social networks.

Criticism: One criticism of IDT is that it may oversimplify the adoption process and overlook the role of power dynamics, cultural factors, and resource constraints that can affect the diffusion of innovations (Greenhalgh et al., 2004).

Relevance and Application: IDT is highly relevant to this study as it helps explain the adoption patterns of sustainable agrifood production practices in Kenya's ASALs. By analyzing the factors that influence the uptake of climate-smart agriculture practices and other innovations, the study can identify strategies to enhance their adoption and scaling.

LITERATURE REVIEW: SUSTAINABLE AGRIFOOD PRODUCTION IN ARID AND SEMI-ARID REGIONS

GLOBAL PERSPECTIVES

United States: Innovative Practices in Arizona

Arizona, located in the southwestern United States, is a prime example of an arid region where innovative agricultural practices have been implemented to address water scarcity and enhance food production. The state has invested in advanced irrigation technologies, such as drip and sprinkler irrigation, to optimize water use efficiency. Additionally, Arizona's agricultural sector has adopted crop varieties that are tolerant to drought and high temperatures, such as sorghum and barley (National Agricultural Statistics Service, 2020). These practices have not only increased crop yields but also reduced water consumption, demonstrating a successful adaptation to arid conditions.

India: The Push for Climate-Smart Agriculture

India, with vast regions experiencing arid and semi-arid conditions, has been a pioneer in promoting Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA). In states like Rajasthan and Gujarat, the government has implemented programs that encourage the adoption of drought-resistant crops, efficient irrigation systems, and soil conservation techniques. One notable initiative is the Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana (PMKSY), which focuses on enhancing water-use efficiency through micro-irrigation and watershed management. The promotion of CSA practices has led to increased agricultural productivity and resilience, particularly in regions vulnerable to climatic variability (Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, 2021).

Samoa and Fiji: Agroforestry and Sustainable Farming

In the Pacific Islands, particularly in Samoa and Fiji, agroforestry has been widely adopted as a sustainable farming practice in response to limited arable land and changing climatic

conditions. These systems integrate trees with crops and livestock, enhancing biodiversity and providing multiple benefits such as soil fertility, water conservation, and climate resilience. In Samoa, the FAO-supported "Agroforestry for Food Security and Climate Resilience" project has been instrumental in promoting these practices. Similarly, in Fiji, traditional agroforestry systems, known as "village gardens," have been revived to improve food security and reduce reliance on imported food (FAO, 2020).

African Context

Ghana: Conservation Agriculture in the Northern Regions

Ghana's northern regions, characterized by semi-arid conditions, have embraced conservation agriculture (CA) as a means to improve soil health and increase crop yields. The adoption of CA practices, including minimum tillage, crop rotation, and the use of cover crops, has been supported by the Ghana Agricultural Sector Investment Programme (GASIP). These practices have led to improved soil moisture retention, reduced erosion, and increased resilience to drought. As a result, farmers in these regions have experienced enhanced food security and livelihoods (FAO, 2019).

Nigeria: Irrigation and Water Management in the Sahel

In the Sahelian regions of Nigeria, where water scarcity is a significant challenge, irrigation and water management practices have been crucial for sustaining agriculture. The establishment of small-scale irrigation schemes, such as the Kano River Irrigation Project, has enabled farmers to cultivate crops year-round. Additionally, the adoption of water-saving technologies, such as sprinkler and drip irrigation, has improved water use efficiency. These initiatives have contributed to increased agricultural productivity and reduced vulnerability to drought, benefiting smallholder farmers in the region (International Water Management Institute, 2018).

Angola, Chad, Libya, and Mali: Dryland Farming and Resilience Building

In the arid regions of Angola, Chad, Libya, and Mali, dryland farming practices have been adopted to enhance resilience to climatic variability. These practices include the use of drought-resistant crop varieties, soil and water conservation techniques, and agroforestry. In Chad, for example, the FAO has supported the promotion of resilient farming systems through the "Sustainable Management of Agricultural Resources" project. Similarly, in Mali, the "Projet de Développement de l'Agriculture au Mali" (PDA-M) has focused on improving water management and promoting sustainable land use practices. These initiatives have contributed to improved food security and resilience in these countries (FAO, 2019).

East African Perspective

Sudan: Integrated Water Resources Management

In Sudan, where arid and semi-arid conditions prevail, integrated water resources management (IWRM) has been a key strategy to enhance agricultural productivity. The Gezira Scheme, one of the largest irrigation projects in the world, exemplifies the country's efforts to optimize water use for agriculture. The scheme has facilitated the cultivation of various crops, including cotton, wheat, and sorghum, contributing significantly to food security and economic development. Additionally, the adoption of CSA practices, such as water harvesting and conservation agriculture, has further improved the resilience of agricultural systems to climatic shocks (El-Gayoum & Ali, 2018).

Somalia: Agro-pastoral Systems and Adaptation Strategies

In Somalia, agro-pastoral systems dominate the agricultural landscape, with communities relying on a combination of crop farming and livestock rearing. The country has faced recurrent droughts, leading to food insecurity and economic instability. In response, various initiatives have focused on promoting drought-tolerant crops, sustainable grazing practices, and water management. The "Building Resilience in Somalia" project, supported by the United Nations and other partners, has been instrumental in enhancing the adaptive capacity of agro-pastoral communities. This project has introduced technologies such as water harvesting and improved seed varieties, helping communities better withstand climatic shocks (United Nations Development Programme, 2019).

Ethiopia: Sustainable Land Management and Climate Resilience

Ethiopia has made significant strides in promoting sustainable land management (SLM) practices, particularly in its arid and semi-arid regions. The country's Sustainable Land Management Program (SLMP) has focused on combating land degradation, improving soil fertility, and enhancing water use efficiency. Key interventions include terracing, reforestation, and the construction of water harvesting structures. These practices have not only improved agricultural productivity but also enhanced the resilience of rural communities to climate change. The success of these initiatives has been attributed to strong government support and community participation (World Bank, 2021).

Tanzania: Climate-Smart Agriculture and Food Security

In Tanzania, the adoption of CSA practices has been pivotal in enhancing food security in arid and semi-arid regions. The country's CSA strategy includes the promotion of drought-resistant crops, efficient irrigation systems, and soil conservation techniques. The "Tanzania Climate-Smart Agriculture Project," supported by the World Bank, aims to increase agricultural productivity and resilience to climate change. The project has facilitated the dissemination of improved seed varieties, training on CSA practices, and the establishment of farmer field schools. These efforts have led to increased crop yields and improved livelihoods for smallholder farmers in the country's ASAL regions (World Bank, 2020).

Kenyan Context

Kenya's ASALs: Sustainable Agrifood Production Initiatives

Kenya's arid and semi-arid lands (ASALs) cover approximately 89% of the country's land area and are home to diverse communities with unique livelihood systems. The ASALs face significant challenges, including water scarcity, land degradation, and frequent droughts. However, various initiatives have been implemented to promote sustainable agrifood production and enhance resilience to climate change.

Turkana County: Agro-pastoralism and Water Management

In Turkana County, agro-pastoralism is a common livelihood strategy. The Turkana Rehabilitation Programme, supported by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and other partners, has focused on promoting sustainable agricultural practices. The program has introduced drought-resistant crops, such as sorghum and millet, and implemented water harvesting and small-scale irrigation systems. These interventions have improved agricultural productivity and food security, providing a buffer against the impacts of drought (FAO, 2021).

Marsabit County: Soil and Water Conservation Techniques

Marsabit County has adopted integrated soil and water conservation techniques to combat soil erosion and enhance agricultural productivity. The Marsabit Integrated Development Programme (MIDP) has promoted practices such as terracing, stone bunds, and zai pits. These methods have helped retain water, reduce soil erosion, and improve soil fertility. Additionally, the promotion of agroforestry has provided fodder, fuel, and additional income for local communities, contributing to improved livelihoods and environmental conservation (Nyangito & Nyandiko, 2022).

Garissa County: Livelihood Diversification through Beekeeping

Garissa County, located in northeastern Kenya, has explored alternative livelihoods to mitigate the impacts of climate change. One successful initiative has been the promotion of beekeeping and honey production. The Beekeeping Enterprise Development Project, supported by various non-governmental organizations (NGOs), has provided training and equipment to local communities, enabling them to engage in commercial honey production. This initiative has increased household incomes and reduced vulnerability to climatic shocks, while also promoting the conservation of indigenous tree species (Mwangi & Mungai, 2021).

Kitui County: Climate-Smart Agriculture Initiatives

Kitui County has been a focal point for the implementation of climate-smart agriculture (CSA) practices. The Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization (KALRO), in collaboration with local government and international partners, has promoted CSA practices, including the use of drought-tolerant crop varieties and conservation tillage. The Kitui Climate-Smart Villages Project aims to build the resilience of smallholder farmers to climate variability by introducing rainwater harvesting, improved seed varieties, and efficient irrigation technologies. These efforts have led to increased agricultural productivity and enhanced adaptive capacity among local farmers (KALRO, 2022).

Isiolo County: Index-Based Livestock Insurance

Isiolo County has faced challenges related to livestock losses due to drought. The Index-Based Livestock Insurance (IBLI) scheme, introduced by the Government of Kenya in partnership with the International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI), provides financial compensation to pastoralists when drought conditions exceed certain thresholds. The IBLI scheme has served as a safety net for pastoralist households, enabling them to recover from livestock losses and maintain their livelihoods. This initiative highlights the importance of innovative financial instruments in building resilience to climate-related risks (ILRI, 2021).

Research Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-methods research design, integrating both qualitative and quantitative approaches. The mixed-methods approach was chosen to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing sustainable agrifood production in Kenya's arid and semi-arid lands (ASALs). The qualitative component involved in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, while the quantitative component included a structured survey and statistical analysis using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

Study Area

The study was conducted in selected ASAL regions of Kenya, including Turkana, Marsabit, Garissa, Kitui, and Isiolo counties. These regions were chosen due to their diverse agro-ecological conditions and the presence of various sustainable agricultural practices, making them ideal for assessing the impacts of climate change adaptation strategies.

Target Population

The target population consisted of smallholder farmers, agro-pastoralists, local government officials, and representatives from non-governmental organizations (NGOs) involved in agricultural development and climate resilience projects. The diverse perspectives provided by these groups offered a holistic view of the challenges and opportunities in promoting sustainable agrifood production in ASALs.

Sampling Techniques

Purposeful Sampling

A purposeful sampling technique was utilized to ensure equal representation of various stakeholders in the study area. This approach allowed for the deliberate selection of participants based on their knowledge, experience, and involvement in sustainable agrifood production practices. Purposeful sampling was particularly useful in identifying key informants who provided rich, in-depth qualitative data.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size for the quantitative component was determined using Cochran's formula for sample size calculation, considering a large population. The formula is given by:

$$n_0 = \frac{Z^2 \times p \times (1-p)}{e^2}$$

Where:

- n_0 is the sample size.
- Z is the Z-score corresponding to the desired confidence level (1.96 for a 95% confidence level).
- p is the estimated proportion of an attribute present in the population (assumed to be 0.5 for maximum variability).
- e is the margin of error (set at 0.05).

Given these parameters, the initial sample size was calculated, and adjustments were made to account for non-response and logistical constraints, resulting in a final sample size of 400 respondents.

Data Collection Methods

Qualitative Data Collection

Qualitative data were collected through semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions. Key informants, including local government officials, NGO representatives, and community leaders, were interviewed to gain insights into the implementation and effectiveness of sustainable agrifood practices. Focus group discussions with smallholder

farmers and agro-pastoralists were conducted to explore their experiences, challenges, and perceptions of climate change adaptation strategies.

Quantitative Data Collection

Quantitative data were collected using a structured survey questionnaire administered to a representative sample of 400 respondents. The questionnaire covered various aspects of sustainable agrifood production, including the adoption of climate-smart agriculture practices, access to resources, and the impact of external support programs. The survey also included questions to measure the perceived effectiveness and sustainability of these practices.

Data Analysis

Qualitative Data Analysis

The qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis, which involved coding the data and identifying key themes and patterns. Thematic analysis facilitated an in-depth understanding of the participants' perspectives and experiences. NVivo software was used to assist in the organization and analysis of qualitative data, allowing for a systematic and rigorous examination of the responses.

Quantitative Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). SEM was employed to test the hypothesized relationships between variables and to assess the overall model fit. The use of SEM was appropriate for this study as it allowed for the examination of complex relationships between multiple variables, including latent constructs and observed indicators.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypotheses were tested using SEM, with model parameters estimated through maximum likelihood estimation. The hypotheses were tested at a 95% confidence level, with significance determined by p-values less than 0.05. The goodness-of-fit indices, including the Chi-square statistic, Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), were used to evaluate the model fit.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring informed consent, confidentiality, and the right to withdraw participation at any time. Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant institutional review board, and participants were fully informed of the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks.

DATA ANALYSIS, INTERPRETATION, AND PRESENTATION

Quantitative Data Analysis

The quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, along with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test the relationships between various factors influencing sustainable agrifood production in Kenya's ASAL regions.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristic	Frequency (n=400)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	260	65
Female	140	35
Age Group		
18-30 years	80	20
31-50 years	230	57.5
51 years and above	90	22.5
Education Level		
No formal education	50	12.5
Primary education	120	30
Secondary education	150	37.5
Tertiary education	80	20
Main Occupation		
Farming	280	70
Agro-pastoralism	100	25
Government/NGO employee	20	5

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The majority were male (65%), aged between 31-50 years (57.5%), with secondary education (37.5%). Most respondents were primarily engaged in farming (70%).

Adoption of Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) Practices

Table 2: Adoption of CSA Practices

CSA Practice	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Drought-resistant crops	300	75
Drip irrigation	100	25
Conservation tillage	220	55
Agroforestry	180	45
Water harvesting techniques	280	70

Table 2 indicates the adoption rates of various CSA practices. The most commonly adopted practices were drought-resistant crops (75%), water harvesting techniques (70%), and conservation tillage (55%).

SEM Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

The SEM analysis tested the hypothesized relationships between CSA practices, external support, resource access, and sustainable agrifood production.

Table 3: SEM Model Fit Indices

Fit Index	Threshold	Model Value
Chi-square (χ^2)	-	280.45
RMSEA	<0.08	0.05
CFI	>0.90	0.92
TLI	>0.90	0.91

Table 3 presents the model fit indices. The SEM model demonstrated a good fit, as indicated by the RMSEA value of 0.05, CFI of 0.92, and TLI of 0.91.

Table 4: Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Standardized Estimate	p-value
H1: CSA practices positively influence sustainable production	0.65	<0.001
H2: External support positively moderates CSA adoption	0.45	<0.01
H3: Access to resources positively influences CSA adoption	0.50	<0.001

Table 4 shows the results of the hypothesis testing. All hypotheses were supported, with significant positive relationships found between CSA practices and sustainable agrifood production (H1), the moderating effect of external support on CSA adoption (H2), and the influence of access to resources on CSA adoption (H3).

Qualitative Data Analysis

Qualitative data from interviews and focus group discussions were analyzed thematically. Key themes identified included challenges in access to water and financial resources, the importance of external support (e.g., government and NGOs), and the benefits of adopting CSA practices.

Table 5: Key Themes from Qualitative Data

Theme	Description
Water scarcity	Participants highlighted water scarcity as a significant challenge, particularly affecting crop irrigation and livestock watering.
Financial constraints	Limited access to credit and financial resources was identified as a barrier to adopting CSA technologies and practices.
Role of external support	External support, including government programs and NGO initiatives, was crucial in providing training, resources, and financial assistance.
Benefits of CSA practices	Participants noted improvements in crop yields, soil fertility, and resilience to climate variability as benefits of adopting CSA practices.

Interpretation and Discussion

The findings from the quantitative and qualitative analyses provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing sustainable agrifood production in Kenya's ASAL regions.

Adoption of CSA Practices

The high adoption rate of drought-resistant crops (75%) and water harvesting techniques (70%) reflects the critical need for water-efficient practices in these regions. These findings are consistent with global trends, as observed in Arizona, USA, where similar practices were adopted to manage water scarcity (National Agricultural Statistics Service, 2020). In India, the promotion of CSA practices under the Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana also highlighted the importance of efficient water use in arid conditions (Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, 2021).

Role of External Support

The SEM analysis revealed that external support positively moderates the adoption of CSA practices (Standardized Estimate = 0.45, $p < 0.01$). This finding aligns with the experiences in Somalia and Ethiopia, where international and government support played a crucial role in enhancing the resilience of agro-pastoral communities and promoting sustainable land management (United Nations Development Programme, 2019; World Bank, 2021). In Kenya, initiatives like the Turkana Rehabilitation Programme and the Kitui Climate-Smart Villages Project have demonstrated the importance of external support in providing training, resources, and financial assistance to local communities (FAO, 2021; KALRO, 2022).

Access to Resources

The positive influence of access to resources on the adoption of CSA practices (Standardized Estimate = 0.50, $p < 0.001$) underscores the importance of financial and material support for smallholder farmers. This finding is consistent with the literature, which highlights financial constraints as a significant barrier to the adoption of innovative agricultural practices (Mwangi & Mungai, 2021). In regions like Garissa and Marsabit, the provision of financial resources

and technical assistance has been crucial in enabling farmers to adopt water-saving technologies and soil conservation techniques (Nyangito & Nyandiko, 2022).

Benefits of CSA Practices

The qualitative data highlighted the benefits of CSA practices, including improved crop yields, soil fertility, and resilience to climate variability. These benefits mirror the outcomes observed in Ghana and Tanzania, where the adoption of CSA practices led to increased agricultural productivity and enhanced food security (FAO, 2019; World Bank, 2020). In Kenya, the adoption of CSA practices in ASAL regions has been instrumental in mitigating the adverse effects of climate change and ensuring sustainable livelihoods for local communities.

Conclusion

The study's findings underscore the critical role of CSA practices, external support, and resource access in promoting sustainable agrifood production in Kenya's ASAL regions. The integration of quantitative and qualitative data provided a holistic understanding of the challenges and opportunities faced by these communities. The positive outcomes associated with CSA adoption highlight the potential for scaling up these practices to enhance food security and resilience in other arid and semi-arid regions. Further research could explore the long-term impacts of these interventions and the potential for integrating new technologies and practices to address emerging challenges in sustainable agrifood production.

SUMMARY OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

This study investigated the factors influencing sustainable agrifood production in Kenya's arid and semi-arid lands (ASALs), focusing on climate-smart agriculture (CSA) practices, the role of external support, and resource access. The research utilized both quantitative and qualitative methods, including surveys, interviews, and focus group discussions.

Key Findings:

1. **Adoption of CSA Practices:** The study found that drought-resistant crops (75%), water harvesting techniques (70%), and conservation tillage (55%) were the most widely adopted CSA practices among respondents. These practices were critical for managing water scarcity and improving agricultural productivity.
2. **Impact of External Support:** External support significantly influenced the adoption of CSA practices. Government and NGO initiatives played a crucial role in providing training, resources, and financial assistance. This support positively moderated the adoption of CSA practices, reflecting similar trends observed in other regions such as Somalia and Ethiopia.
3. **Access to Resources:** Access to financial resources and materials was a significant factor in the adoption of CSA practices. Limited access to credit and other financial resources was identified as a major barrier, aligning with findings from previous research on financial constraints in agricultural development.
4. **Benefits of CSA Practices:** Qualitative data indicated that CSA practices led to improved crop yields, soil fertility, and enhanced resilience to climate variability. These benefits were consistent with outcomes reported in other countries, including Ghana and Tanzania.

Conclusions

The research highlighted several critical aspects of promoting sustainable agrifood production in Kenya's ASAL regions:

1. **Effectiveness of CSA Practices:** The adoption of CSA practices significantly contributes to sustainable agricultural production and resilience in ASAL regions. The practices adopted by local farmers have proven effective in addressing the challenges of water scarcity and soil degradation.
2. **Importance of External Support:** External support, including government and NGO initiatives, is essential for facilitating the adoption of CSA practices. These programs provide necessary resources, training, and financial assistance that enable farmers to implement and sustain CSA practices.
3. **Resource Access:** Access to financial resources and materials is crucial for the successful adoption of CSA practices. Financial constraints remain a significant barrier, impacting the ability of smallholder farmers to invest in and maintain these practices.

Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Strengthening External Support:** Continued investment in government and NGO programs that provide training, resources, and financial assistance to farmers is essential. Expanding these programs to reach more communities and enhance their effectiveness could improve the adoption and impact of CSA practices.
2. **Improving Access to Resources:** Efforts should be made to improve access to financial resources for smallholder farmers. This could include developing microfinance schemes, providing subsidies for CSA technologies, and enhancing access to credit facilities.
3. **Promoting CSA Awareness:** Increased awareness and education about the benefits of CSA practices should be promoted. Community-based extension services and training programs can help farmers better understand and implement CSA practices effectively.
4. **Enhancing Collaboration:** Collaboration between government agencies, NGOs, and local communities should be strengthened to ensure a coordinated approach to sustainable agrifood production. Partnerships can help in resource mobilization, knowledge sharing, and implementing best practices.

Areas for Future Studies

1. **Long-Term Impacts of CSA Practices:** Future research could focus on the long-term impacts of CSA practices on agricultural productivity, soil health, and food security. Longitudinal studies could provide insights into the sustained benefits and challenges of CSA adoption over time.
2. **Effectiveness of Different Types of Support:** Investigating the effectiveness of various types of external support (e.g., financial aid, technical assistance) in promoting CSA adoption could provide valuable insights into optimizing support programs.
3. **Economic Implications of CSA Practices:** Further research could explore the economic implications of CSA practices, including cost-benefit analyses, return on investment, and the economic viability of different CSA technologies.

4. **Comparative Studies Across Regions:** Comparative studies examining the adoption and impacts of CSA practices in different ASAL regions or countries could provide a broader understanding of regional variations and best practices in sustainable agrifood production.

By addressing these areas, future research can contribute to more effective strategies for promoting sustainable agrifood production and building resilience in arid and semi-arid regions.

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